
Fostering Inter-Ethnic Unity and Mutuality in West Africa Through Language: French

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the role of the French language as a strategic tool for fostering inter-ethnic unity and mutual cooperation in West Africa, a region characterized by vast linguistic and cultural diversity with hundreds of indigenous languages often limiting cross-border communication. The presence of French as a shared medium among several countries offers opportunities for dialogue, integration and peaceful coexistence. A common language enhances unity and mutuality which is a pivot to growth, development, progress, advancement etc. of West African countries. It is a known fact that no nation can be an island on its own. There must be interactions between nations of different ethnic groups in order to achieve the desired goals. French as an official or second language in many states, facilitates education, trade, diplomacy, and regional mobility, thereby reducing ethnic barriers and strengthening socio-political ties. It is in the light of this that the paper hinges on theory of social interdependence which postulates that, the accomplishment of each individual's goals is affected by the actions of others. Fostering close relations among ethnic groups especially in West African cannot be possible without language. The paper argues that beyond its colonial origin, French has evolved into a functional lingua franca that promotes intercultural understanding and collective development within regional institution such as Economic Community of West African States. Through examples from education, commerce and intergovernmental relations, the study highlights how the language encourages cooperation, conflict resolution and shared identity among diverse ethnic groups. The paper concludes that effective language policies, inclusive educational practices, and multilingual strategies can maximize the integrative potential of French while preserving indigenous linguistic heritage. French language therefore remains a valuable instrument for regional cohesion and sustainable development in West

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1.0. INTRODUCTION

West Africa is one of the most linguistically and culturally diverse regions of the world. Within the same geographical space exist numerous ethnic groups, each with its own language, traditions, and worldview. While this diversity represents cultural richness, it often poses serious communication challenges that can hinder cooperation, economic progress and peaceful coexistence among neighboring communities and states. In many cases, the absence of a common linguistic platform contributes to misunderstanding, ethnic suspicion and limited interaction across borders. A French adage says 'l'union fait la force' which means united we stand, divided we fall. Unity is the bedrock of development, progress, peace, security etc in any country. Mutual inter-dependency of nations fast track progress, development and growth since no nation can be an island on her own. For these to take place, communication is very crucial. Communication is a strong factor that enhances smooth and cordial relationship among the nations of the world. A country cannot grow without effective internal and external communication system and this cannot take place outside language. On international scene for instance, the major languages in West Africa cannot bear the burden of communication. It is a vital means by which people exchange information, share ideas and feelings describe and project their inner and outer world, recreate things. The importance of language and communication cannot be overemphasized in this century. Kelman (1971) quoted by Oyetade (2001:14) describes language as, "a powerful instrument in unifying a diverse population and in involving individuals and subgroups in the national system". Another definition of language that is relevant to our subject

matter is equally given by Oyetade (2001) citing Block and Trager (1942), describing language ‘as a system of arbitrary vocal symbols by which a social group operates.’ These two definitions emphasized the co-operative function of language i.e holding people together for a common goal. Language is therefore important if there is going to be any meaningful co-existence between the nations of the world. So, it is a known fact all over the world that communication is a strong factor for smooth and cordial relationship among the whole world in general. Alo (2005:5) views communication as a vital means by which people exchange information, share ideas and feelings, project their inner and outer world, recreate things. In this century the importance of communication cannot be over stressed because we cannot interact exchange views with one another without using language.

Language plays crucial role in social integration because it serves as the primary medium through which ideas, values and identities are shared. In this regard, French has emerged as an important bridge language in the region. French enables communication among populations that do not share indigenous languages. It also facilitates cross- border collaboration and participation in regional framework thereby promoting solidarity and collective development. French functions as a practical tool for inter-ethnic dialogue and mutual understanding. By providing a common linguistic ground, it encourages mobility, strengthen institutional cooperation and upport peaceful relations among diverse groups.

The paper therefore explores how French can be harnessed to foster inter -ethnic unity and mutuality in West Africa.

2.0. FRENCH LANGUAGE

According to Ade- Ojo (2002; 2) French language ranks the 2nd international language taught in the world. It is very important in every field of human endeavour, be it commerce, science, technology, culture, diplomatic, politics, tourism and so on.

French is part of a group of languages known as Romance languages (also including Italian, Spanish, Portuguese and Romanian) because they descended from Latin, the language of the ancient Romans. This contrasts with English, which is classified as a Germanic language (also including German, Dutch, Danish, Norwegian, Swedish etc). Although there are great differences between these language groups, they all nevertheless derive from the same family of languages called Indo-European languages. These languages are thought to have originated around the black sea (modern day Ukraine) around 6000BC, before the population movements, possibly for environmental reasons such as climate change or exhaustion of pastures, caused the dispersion throughout Asian and Europe during the millennium 4000BC-3000BC. Because of this dispersion, subgroups of Indo-European languages began to develop in isolation, causing the formation of the various groups mentioned above.

The RealFrench.net website accessed 13th August 2014 opines that French language owes its existence to a number of ancient languages. These include:

~ Gaulish, the language of the Celtic peoples (of which the fictional Asterix the Gaal was one) who inhabited primarily the territory of what is now modern-day France, prior to the Romans evasions.

~ Latin, the language of the invading Romans.

~ Frankish, the language of the Germanic people who occupied this territory after the fall of the Roman Empire, and who gave France its name.

~ Old Norse, the language of the Vikings, who occupied many of the Coastal and inland navigable areas of Northern France before being granted the area now known as Novmandy (meaning land of the Norsemen).

It was during the 20th century that French was fully established as the national language of France. From around the time of Louis XIV to the beginning of the 20th century French was very much viewed as the language of international communication within European-influenced Countries. This situation probably arose out of a number of factors including the consistent political power that France enjoyed during this time, its geographical position at the heart of Europe, its strong historical relations with all the major western nations, its immense cultural prestige both in terms of the arts and in terms of ‘cultural living’ (food, wine, fashion, furniture etc) aspects that were important to the international diplomatic set. Various factors, most notably the dominance of the United States in international politics, commerce, technology and popular culture, have meant that it is now English and not French that is the dominant international language. However, in many ways French still retains its roles as an international language of communication, being an official language in most of the major international organizations such as the United Nations

La francophonie dans le monde 2006-2007 also submits that :

- 128 million francophones: speak French as a native or adopted language fluently and use it on regular basis.72 million “partial” francophones: live in a francophone country but do not speak French regularly, due to limited knowledge.
- 100-110 million students of all ages: do not live in a francophone country, but have learned or are learning French in order to communicate with francophone.

French is also the official language of certain regions of multilingual countries such as: Belgium, Wallonie region Canada, Quebec province, Switzerland: Jura, Geneva, Neuchatel and Vaud districts. Also, French is equally the official language in the following countries: Belgium, Burundi, Cameroon, Canada, Chad, Channel Islands (Guernsey and jersey), Camows, Djibouti, Equatorial Guinea, Haiti, (the other official language in French credo), Madagascar, Rwanda], Seychelles, Switzerland, Vanuatu.

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French is considered an international language not only because it is spoken in dozens of countries, but also because it is one of the official working languages in many international organizations, including: African Union (AU) (5), Amnesty International (4), Council of Europe (2), European Commission (3), Interpol (4), International Criminal Court (2), International Olympic committee (2), International organization for standardization (2), International Red Cross and Red Crescent (3), Medicines sans Frontiers (doctors without border)(1), North American Free Trade Agreement(3) North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2) Organization for Economic Cooperation Development(2), United Nations(6), World Health Organization (6), World Trade Organization (3). The number (in parentheses) indicates the total number of official working languages for that organization.

In multilingual societies, especially in Africa, French often serves as a neutral bridge language that enables communication among people from different ethnic and linguistic backgrounds. Consequently, the French language is not only a tool for expression but also an instrument for unity, cooperation and socio-economic development in diverse communities.

3.0. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework adopted for this paper is social interdependence theory by Johnson and Johnson. Social interdependence exists when the accomplishment of each individual's goals is affected by the actions of others (Deutsch, 1949, 1962; Johnson, 1970; D. W. Johnson & R. Johnson, 1989). There are two types of social interdependence. The positive (cooperation) and negative (competition).

- Positive interdependence exists when individuals perceive that they can reach their goals if and only if the other individuals with whom they are cooperatively linked also reach their goals and, therefore, promote each other's efforts to achieve the goals.
- Negative interdependence exists when individuals perceive that they can obtain their goals if and only if the other individuals with whom they are competitively linked fail to obtain their goals and, therefore, obstruct each other's efforts to achieve the goals.
- No interdependence results in a situation in which individuals perceive that they can reach their goal regardless of whether other individuals in the situation attain or do not attain their goals.

Source: Johnson and Johnson (1995)

PSYCHOLOGICAL PROCESSES

The psychological processes created by positive interdependence include substitutability (the degree to which actions of one person substitute for the actions of another person), Inducibility (openness to being influenced and to influencing others), and positive cathexis (Investment of positive psychological energy in objects outside of oneself) (Deutsch, 1949, 1962).

These processes explain how self-interest is expanded to joint interest and how new goals and motives are created in cooperative and competitive situations. Self-interest becomes expanded to mutual interest through other people's actions substituting for one's own, through an emotional investment in achieving goals (that benefit others as well as oneself and generalizes to caring and committed relationships with those who are working for the same purposes and goals), and through an openness to being influenced so that joint efforts are more effective.

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Demonstrating the transition from self-interest to mutual interest is perhaps one of the most important aspects of social interdependence theory. Positive interdependence results in promotive interaction, negative interdependence results in oppositional or contrient interaction, and no interdependence results in the absence of interaction.

Promotive interaction may be defined as individuals encouraging and facilitating each other's efforts to complete tasks, achieve, or produce in order to reach the group's goals. It consists of a number of variables, including mutual help and assistance, exchange of needed resources, effective communication, mutual influence, trust, and constructive management of conflict.

4.0. THE PLACE OF FRENCH IN FOSTERING INTER-ETHNIC UNITY AND MUTUALITY IN WEST AFRICA.

4.1. Intergovernmental Relations and Diplomacy.

The West African leaders were aware of the place of a strong economy in an International Community hence, one of the reasons why the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) was formed on May 28th, 1975 is to aid and foster economic growth and development. The Organization was also formed to increase and maintain the economic stability of the member-States by fostering close relations among its members (Oni 1980: 113). West Africa, region of the western African continent was defined by the United Nations as the 16 countries of Nigeria, Togo, Ghana, Liberia, Senegal, Mauritania, Sierra-Leone, Guinea Bissau, Ivory Coast, Guinea, Niger, Mali, Benin and Burkina . These sixteen countries consist of five English speaking countries, two Portuguese speaking countries while the remaining nine are French speaking countries. A closer look at the table below reveals the preponderance of French-speaking countries in West-Africa as compared with their English-speaking counterparts. Similarly, there is only one representative of the Lusophone, i.e. Guinea Bissau. We can therefore say that, the European languages, especially French, command great prestige among West Africans and indeed all over Africa.

Table showing: West African countries with their official and major languages

COUNTRY	OFFICIAL LANGUAGE	MAJOR LANGUAGES
Burkina Faso	French	Moore
Benin	French	Fon-Ewe, Yoruba, Bariba
Cameroon	French/English	Bamileke, Fang, Ewando, Fulfude, Bulu
Cote d'ivoire	French	Akan, Dyula, Anyi-Baoule, Senoufo
Ghana	English	Akan, Dagbani, Ewe, Hausa, Adangme, Ga, Dagari
The Gambia	English	Mandigo, Wolof
Guinea	French	Malinke, Fulfulde, Sousou
Guinea Bissau	Portuguese	Crioulo
Liberia	English	Bassa, Kpelle, Krio
Mali	French	Bambara, Fulfulde, Arabic
Mauretania	French	Arabic, Fulfulde, Wolof
Niger	French	Hausa, Songhai, Tamashek
Nigeria	English	Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo, Fulfulde, Pidgin, Kanuri, Edo, Ijaw, Efik, Idoma
Senegal	French	Wolof, Fulfulde, Serer, Diola, Malinke, Soninke
Sierra Leone	English	Mende, Temne, Krio
Togo	French	Ewe, Kabiye, Hausa

(Adapted from Oyetade 2001:42)

The Economy Community of West African States (ECOWAS) was created on May 28th 1975 by these sixteen West African Countries in the table. The organization was formed because the leaders were aware of the place of strong economy in an international community in the first place and again, according to Oni (1980:113) the ECOWAS was formed to increase and maintain the economic stability of its member-states by fostering close relations among its members, to promote cooperation and integration in order to create an economic and monetary growth and development in West Africa. The founding fathers of

ECOWAS also recognized the potentials of language as a factor of integration, unity and mutuality. Therefore, in the treaty of May 28th 1975, it is stated in Article 58, page 75 thus `the official language of the community shall be such African languages declared official by the Authority and `English and French`. No West African language or languages have been declared as official languages in order to prevent breakdown in communication. A breakdown in communication often leads to misunderstanding, suspicion and lack of trust among people living together.

In this 21st century, the importance of communication cannot be overemphasized. It is a fact that, we cannot interact, exchange views with one another without using language. Language and communication are the life wire that regulates the essence of human beings and organizations.

It has been said earlier that, united we stand divided we fall. Unity among West African countries is very imperative because no country can be an Island on her own and develop or grow in all necessary areas. The major languages of those countries cannot bear the burden of international communication. Language is therefore relevant as far as regional growth is concerned. In order to remove language barrier, the use of French and English languages have been emphasized as the language of business, commerce, and politics and of interaction by the body.

4.2 Peacebuilding and Conflict Resolution

The role of French language in conflict Resolution cannot be over-emphasized. Ethnic conflicts are bound to occur when people with diverse cultures, economic conditions and political systems are brought together regardless of their dissimilarities. There was a time Major General Olusegun Obasanjo, the former President of Nigeria closed all borders that lead to Nigeria because it was discovered that Armed Robbers do come from the Republic of Benin to cause havoc on Nigerian citizens. All efforts to get them were abortive until Nigerian Government decided to close all borders. The decision of the government was too powerful and unbearable for them at Republic of Benin. Because of this, a powerful delegate led by the President of Benin himself came to Abuja to dialogue with the government of Nigeria. The conditions for peace were spelt out and the matter was amicably resolved. The bandit leader (Shina Rambo) was handed over to the Nigerian government for trial. The dialogue could not be possible without language.

Inter-ethnic marriage is also possible through language. For instance, Nigerians, Beninois/es, Cameroonians, Congolese, Togolese, Ivoirians etc can marry themselves without any problem with the aid of language. The knowledge of French can make or encourage an African man to marry an European woman.

Language enhances cooperation, togetherness and oneness. During this trying period of Nigeria with Boko Haram insurgency, different countries of the world showed interest in assisting Nigeria to fight the menace. Various meetings were held, and steps were taken in order to assist Nigeria and to rescue those Chibok girls who are in the custody of the Boko Haram people.

The West African countries need to relate with Francophone countries like France and others that are already developed technologically, politically, and economically. This relationship cannot be possible without language. Speaking an international language (French) should be seen as central or pivot in our efforts to develop in all areas.

A shared language enables dialogue during disputes, helping communities discuss grievances, negotiate solutions and maintain peaceful co existence

4.3. Trade and Economic Activities

French facilitates cross-border commerce by enabling traders, entrepreneurs, and investors from different ethnic groups to communicate effectively. This promotes trust, partnerships and economic interdependence.

4.4 Media and Information Sharing

Radio, television, newspaper and digital platforms in French help disseminate information across diverse communities. shared access to news and public discourse strengthens collective awareness and national or regional identity.

4.5. Education

French serves as a common medium of instruction in schools and universities, allowing learners from different ethnic backgrounds to study together, interact freely, and exchange ideas. This shared academic environment reduces ethnic isolation and builds mutual respect among students

Therefore, the teaching and learning of this language should not be handled with levity in the affected countries. Languages most especially the foreign languages such as French and English should be seen as a sine qua non to uplift the standard of individual and society at large. Efforts should be made by government to encourage the teaching and learning of these languages at all quarters necessary.

4.6 Cultural Exchange

Through literature, music, theatre and festivals expressed in French, people from various ethnic groups share their traditions and values. This encourages appreciation of cultural diversity rather than division.

4.7. Mobility and Migration

French allows individuals to travel, work and settle easily in neighboring countries without major language barriers. Such mobility promotes social integration and intercultural friendships.

4.8. Administrative and Public Services

Government services conducted in French ensure that citizens from different linguistic backgrounds can access legal, health and civic information equally, fostering inclusion and fairness.

5.0. RECOMMENDATIONS

To enhance the role of the French language in promoting inter-ethnic unity and mutual cooperation, several practical steps should be considered.

Necessary encouragement and motivation needed by students learning this language should be given to them by the parents, the teachers, the government and different schools where this subject is being offered. Measures to learn this language should be put in place for all learners especially in Nigeria, a country that is surrounded by Francophone countries. Government should strengthen French language education at all levels by providing adequate funding, qualified teachers and modern teaching materials. Government should assist students that are learning this language in higher institution of learning especially in the area of acculturation. They should be assisted to travel abroad in order to learn and be able to speak it like native speakers. Different incentives should be made available by government to encourage those that are interested in learning the language. Individuals should also be ready to learn the language due to benefits that could be derived from its knowledge.

CONCLUSION

Language has a lot to do as far as regional growth, development, progress peace etc is concerned. From our submission in this paper, language is the cement that holds people of different ethnic groups together, especially in this century that the whole world has become a global village. Restricting oneself to indigenous languages alone may not be good enough. Effective communication among various ethnic groups leads to peaceful co-existence, growth and development, co-operation, love, forgiveness and others. Therefore, this language (French) should be seen as a means of getting things done among various ethnic groups in West Africa especially Nigeria. Efforts should be made by International societies to promote the learning of the language. More so, when one considers French against the background of the Nations in West Africa; one sees that majority of the Nations have French as their Lingua Franca.

Therefore, strengthening the functional use of French alongside indigenous language remains a viable strategy for promoting inter-ethnic harmony, regional solidarity and shared development across West Africa.

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